

TOMATO POSTHARVEST HANDLERS BY THE RHIZOME EXTRACT OF CYPERUS ROTUNDUS

Panji Rahmatullah^{1*}, Asri Mutia Sani¹, Alfi Muntafi Ilma¹, M. Subandi¹

¹ Department of Agrotechnology, Science and Technology Faculty of Sunan Gunung Djati State Islamic University Bandung, Indonesia. Jalan A.H. Nasution No. 105, Cipadung, Cibiru, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia.

panjirahmatullah@outlook.com

Abstract

Tomato is a commodity that is widely cultivated in Indonesia. The abundance of tomato crops in Indonesia causes unstable tomato prices in the local market. One of solutions to this problems is by exporting tomatoes to another country. However, durability of tomato during storage is still a constraint. This can happens because the tomatoes are stricken with microbes and various post-harvest pest. It has been known that the rhizome of java grass (*Cyperus rotundus* L) that grows wild in Indonesia contains antimicrobial compounds that are able to prevent the growth and the arrival of various types of microbes and post-harvest pests. This study aims to determine the influence of antimicrobial content of rhizome extract of java grass (REJG) towards growth and the presence of microbes and post-harvest pest on tomatoes, in effort to improve the durability of tomato during storage. This research method using Completely Randomized Design repeated 9 times with 4 treatments; P1 = Control, P2 = 100gr/L REJG , P3 = 200gr/L REJG P4 = 300gr/L REJG. The results indicate treatment P2 (100gr/L REJG) is the best formulation capable to increasing durability of tomato by suppressing and preventing the growth of microbes and various post-harvest pest based on the percentage of weight loss, texture score, and the level of decay of tomato.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2549078

1. Introduction

Tomatoes (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) are horticultural products which are widely cultivated and consumed in Indonesia. The largest tomato plant are produced from West Java Province, amounted to 35.26%^[1]. Abundant presence of tomatoes is not uncommon to be a problem when the market is unable to accommodate tomatoes for sale. This refers to the problem of the least targeted market and the perishable tomato situation^[2].

In the year 2015, an incident occurred where tomato farmers in Garut West Java threw their tomatoes harvest into the streets, ditches or even left it in the tree stalk until it has been dried up by itself. This was happened due to the price of tomatoes were very dropped down. At that time, tomato's price from farmers only sold for Rp 200/kg, which is the total revenue of tomatoes lower than the production cost. Therefore, Garut tomato farmers got huge losses. This can be caused by a considerable difference between the amount of tomato's production and the national tomato's demand.

According to Indonesia's Statistic Center^[3] tomato consumption in the year reached 940,000 tons while the production of tomato was 992,780 tons. Which means that there was a considerable difference between the demand and availability of tomatoes, so that 52,780 tons of

tomatoes were wasted in that year. Beside, Indonesia has a great opportunity to triumph as a tomato exporter country. For example, according to Linda and Firdaus^[4] Indonesia should increase its competitiveness in tomato exports to Malaysia and Singapore. In this case, Indonesia competes with Netherlands and China. Although the competitiveness of the Dutch is triumph to Indonesia, but Indonesia is still triumph to China. In addition, Indonesia has the opportunity to be triumph to the Netherlands and China as seen from the performance (based on EPD analysis: Export Product Dynamics). However, there are several problems in tomato export process. One of them is due to perishable character on tomato which occurs due to metabolic processes in tomatoes, high levels of respiration and transpiration, and also high microbial contamination that can cause post-harvest losses of up to 25%^[5].

The chance of microbes to grow on tomatoes is higher due to the physical properties of tomatoes that contain lots of water and thin soft tomato's peel. Physical conditions like that also causes tomatoes easily damaged^[6]. In damaged conditions tomatoes become more damp on the part of damaged and absolutely increasing the chances of microbes to grow^[2]. The growth of these microbes can accelerate the decay percentage of tomato. Not only on damaged tomatoes, the microbes can also spread to the fresh tomatoes. Biologically, protection against microbes and the postharvest pests on tomatoes can be done by coating tomatoes with antimicrobial compounds that are able to control harmful microbes and postharvest pests. It is known that the compound of antimicrobial is contained in rhizome of java grass. Therefore, the tomato's storability can increase, then farmers can export tomatoes for wider market and also get higher income.

Java Grass (*Cyperus rotundus* L.) is a growing plant in Indonesia and many countries in the world, both in tropical and subtropical countries^[7]. Java Grass is highly capable to live in various soils and climates^[8]. Due to its abundant presence, the scientist encourages to get to know about this grass, in order to take its advantages and to be more useful for humans. In many Asian countries, java grass rhizomes has been commonly used as a traditional medicine to treat various diseases^[9]. According to Rahmayanti^[10] states that the rhizome of java grass contains flavonoid to enhance the effectiveness of vitamin C, sesquiterpenoid which is useful as antimicrobial, and alkaloid which is useful as antifungus and insect repellent^[10]. In addition, Bañez and Castor^[11] states that the content which contained in java grass rhizomes is more effective than carbamate pesticides in the insecticidal properties of ants, aphids, and fruit flies. So it can be seen that the contents of java grass rhizomes can be used to control the microbes and various post-harvest pests in tomatoes, but still safe if consumed by humans.

Postharvest handlers aim to keep product quality in line with the consumers wishes^[2]. Nowadays, many kinds of research have been developed to improve the storability of horticultural products. For example, the application of edible coating, edible film, waxing, curing, lighting engineering^[12], drying, and others. However, these methods require quite expensive tools and materials, which absolutely can increase the selling price of tomatoes. Due to the processing and its applications are difficult, these methods can only be done by people who are experts in postharvest field. Therefore it is necessary to develop post-harvest treatment methods that are cheap and easy but still effective in terms of improving the quality of tomatoes. The farmers also can applied this method and the tomato's price is remain stable.

Therefore, in the present study antimicrobial coating from rhizome extract of java grass was investigated in order to press the growth of microbes and postharvest pests so can be known its effect on increasing the storability and quality of tomatoes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plant material

The tomatoes were used in this study are tomatoes which are already in a ready for sale condition and bought at some market in Karawang. The tomatoes has a uniform color that was yellowish green and in uniform texture and maturity conditions. Cyperus rotundus rhizomes were collected from about plantation and abandoned land in Karawang, West Java on 27th June 2018 – 30th June 2018. The java grass rhizomes were dried at room temperature with ventilation for 3 days after being washed with water. The rhizome extract's solution was made using 600 g of rhizomes. The grass rhizomes are weighed according to the required concentration level, then put the rhizomes into a blender and mashed it with 1 liter of water and 10 milliliters of solvent sufractant. After that, the rhizome of java grass is filtered to separate the extract solution and dregs of java grass rhizome so we obtained the certain amount of rhizome extract's solution in accordance with the required level of concentration

2.2 Research Method

This research used Completely Randomized Design with one factor involved, which is the concentrations of java grass rhizome extract (100gr/L,200gr/L, dan 300gr/L). The tomatoes that was being used were half ripe yellowish green tomatoes, stored at room temperature for 11 days. The control was tomatoes without any treatment. The data of this research was analyzed by Variance analysis (ANOVA) and further result was analyzed by Duncan Multiple Range Test to determine the effect of the treatment toward the sensoric attribute characteristic, weight loss and decay loss percentage of the tomatoes.

The storability test of Tomato is done by dipping all parts of tomato into rhizome extract of java grass in each concentration for 3 minutes time immersion. After dipping, the tomatoes are being dried and observed for 11 days from day 1, day 3, day 5, day 7, day 9 and day 11. After applying of rhizome extract java grass, the tomatoes were observed towards weight loss percentage, decay rate ,and the texture score. The tomatoes were compared with the control of the tomatoes that were not dipped in rhizome extract of java grass.

2.3 Weight loss percentage

Measurement of weight loss was done by gravimetry method, that is comparing the difference of weight before storage with after storage. Percent weight loss can be calculated by the formula:

$$\% \text{ Weight loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100\%$$

2.4 Decay loss rate

Determination of decay loss value on tomato is done by doing visual observation analysis on tomato as a whole and compared by the score below:

Table 1 Decay loss scale

Description	Score
<i>Extreme</i> , not edible	1
<i>Severe</i> , still edible but not worth	3
<i>Moderate</i> , there is damage that can interfere the feasibility of tomatoes	5

<i>Slight</i> , there is little damage that may interfere the feasibility of tomatoes	7
<i>None</i> , no damage	9

2.5 Sensory Test

Sensory test was carried out to determine the effect of java grass rhizome extract on the level of panelist acceptance. Sensory test is performed by scalar test / scoring. Panelists are asked to rate the scores that provided. Test parameters include texture and color. This test was undertaken on 11 days after coating treatment. The scoring scale that used was:

Table 2 Scale score for texture assessment of tomato

Texture Description	Score
<i>Extremely poor</i> (loose texture)	1
<i>Poor</i> (the physical component is still intact)	3
<i>Fair</i> (the structure is still compact)	5
<i>Good</i> (the structure is compact and solid)	7
<i>Excellent</i> (the structure is solid)	9

Table 3 Scale score for color assessment of tomato

Color Description	Score
<i>Red</i> (More than 90% of the tomato surface is red)	1
<i>Pink</i> (Red colour shows on over 30% but less than 90% of the tomato surface)	3
<i>Turning</i> (Red colour shows on over 10% but less than 30% of the tomato surface)	5

3. Results and Discussions

At the time of the 11 days of observing the storability of tomato a variety of tomato conditions occur on day 11. Explanation of the condition can be known through the table below:

Level of Concentrations	Tomato Description
0gr/L (Control)	There were 2 tomatoes that has been decayed so that the round shape of the tomatoes disappeared, 4 tomatoes were in a soft condition and there were fungi in them. 3 tomatoes can still in good condition
100gr/L	There were 4 tomatoes that has been already in soft and there were a bit fungi in them, 5 tomatoes still in good condition
200gr/L	There were 3 tomatoes that has been already in soft and there were a bit fungi in them, 6 tomatoes still in good condition

300gr/L

There were 4 tomatoes that has been already in soft and there were a bit fungi in them, 5 tomatoes still in good condition

3.1 Weight loss percentage

The weight loss in tomato is the process of weight loss due to the process of respiration, transpiration and microbes activity. Respiration in fruits is a biological process in which oxygen is absorbed to process organic matter in fruits to produce energy and followed by the release of residual combustion of carbon dioxide and water. The water and the gas that produced and the heat energy will evaporate, so that the fruit will loss its weight^[13]. While the transpiration process is water loss due to evaporation. Evaporation occurs because there are differences in water pressure outside and inside the fruit. The water pressure inside the fruit is higher so that the moisture gets out of the fruit. In addition to the process of transpiration and respiration, weight loss can also be caused by microorganisms that damage the cell structure, such as the use of carbohydrates as substrates for its development.

Figure 1 Percentage of tomato weight loss at several level of concentrations (%). different symbols express the sample issignificantly different at the 0.05 significance level

Measurement of weight loss on tomatoes for 11 days storage process and observation at room temperature increasing in all treatments. Tomatoes which were treated with rhizome extract of java grass have a weight loss value of 11.69% - 12.19%, which was significantly different from tomatoes without given any treatment, namely 16.34%. According to these data, it can be seen that the rhizome extract of java grass significantly affects the percentage of tomato weight loss. This can be caused due to the antimicrobial content that contained in rhizome extract of java grass successfully inhibits pathogenic bacteria and spoilage microorganisms, including fungi that cause damage to the structure of tomato cells, so as to minimize the loss of tomato weight which is also caused by the process of respiration and transpiration.

3.2 Decay loss rating test

Decay loss rating is a test of the level of tomato decay which done by analyzing visual observations on the tomato as a whole and compared with the score rating used

Figure 2 Rating score the decay of the tomato at several level of concentrations. different symbols express the sample is significantly different at the 0.05 significance level

Based on the data above, it can be seen that tomatoes which were not treated (control), had the lowest score of 5.22 and were significantly different from all tomatoes treated with rhizome extract of java grass. Low scores on control tomatoes can be caused by the condition of the tomato was being in bad condition and some tomatoes have been infected with several diseases of the fungus such as Antraknosa (*Colletotrichum coccodes*) and Alternaria (*Alternaria solani*). Whereas in tomatoes that were immersed in the rhizome extract java grass, these fungus was no found. This can be caused by the flavanoid content in rhizome extract java grass successfully inhibit the growth of fungi and bacteria by denaturing the protein bonds in the cell membrane so that the cell membrane into lysis and the compound into the cell nucleus, causing the fungus can not develop^[14]. This causes the several of tomatoes that has been treated with the extract of java grass rhizomes is still in good condition on the 11th day of storage.

3.3 Sensory rating test

3.3.1 Texture

Texture is one of the quality attributes of a product. At the time of storage, the tomato will run into a decrease in the hardness of tomatoes due to depolymerization of carbohydrates and pectin constituents then result in decreasing of viscosity and tomato texture becomes soft^[15]. In addition, the factors that affect the hardness of tomatoes is a destructive microbial activity in tomato cell structure, such as gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas* sp or *Enterobacteriaceae* which have pectinolytic activity^[16].

Figure 3 Rating score the texture of the tomato at several level of concentrations. different symbols express the sample is significantly different at the 0.05 significance level

Based on the above data it can be seen that the untreated tomato (control) has the lowest score value of 5.00 and it was significantly different with all the tomatoes treated with rhizome extracts of java grass. This suggests that the rhizome extract of java grass has

an antimicrobial such as sesquiterpenoid effect that was able to maintain the hardness of the tomatoes.

3.3.2 Color

Three important aspects of receiving a product are color, taste, and texture. Color is the most important factor in terms of acceptance, because if the product looks unattractive, consumers will reject the product without regard to other factors^[17]. Tomato color maturity is characterized by increasing levels of redness caused by degradation of chlorophyll and increased carotenoid synthesis so that the red color intensity is stronger^[18].

Figure 4 Rating score the color of the tomato at several level of concentrations. different symbols express the sample is significantly different at the 0.05 significance level

Based on the data above, tomatoes without treatment (control) have the lowest score, which means that there were several tomatoes that have been red in color as a whole. However, it was not significantly different from tomatoes treated with rhizome extract of java grass. This indicates that immersion with the rhizome extract of java grass cannot affect the ripening process of the tomato. Because the ripening process of tomatoes is a physiological activity of the tomatoes themselves, Millerd et.al.^[19] while the microbes in tomatoes only affect the decay or damage to tomatoes.

4. Conclusion

Tomato coating with antimicrobial rhizome of java grass extract significantly affected the increase of tomato fruit's storability which can be seen from the low loose value of tomato weight, low level of tomato damage, and good tomato hardness / texture on tomatoes that given rhizome extract of java grass in all level of concentration. However, the antimicrobial coating does not significantly affect the level of color maturity score in tomatoes in all levels of rhizome extract of java grass concentration. Based on the results of these studies, it is hoped that this study can be useful to be applied to small or large scale tomato farmers to improve the quality of their tomato crops. If the quality of tomatoes is in maximum condition, then tomatoes that are cultivated in Indonesia are not only for the local market, but also can be marketed abroad. So that Indonesia's tomato export production increases, tomato prices are stable in the local market, and tomato farmers are increasingly prosperous.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Forecasting Center of Pest Management, Karawang that has provided place and supporting equipment in this study and also thanks to Mr. Subandi and Mrs Ida who have guided the author in completing this paper.

References

- [1] [PDSIP] Pusat Data dan Sistem Informasi Pertanian Sekretaris Jendral Kementerian Pertanian. 2014. Outlook Komoditi Tomat. Jakarta (ID): Pusat Data dan Sistem Informasi Pertanian hal.14
- [2] David, John dan C. Kilmanun, Juliana. 2016. Penanganan Pasca Panen Penyimpanan untuk Komoditas Hortikultura. *Balai Pengkajian Teknologi Pertanian Kalimantan Barat*. Di dalam: Seminar Nasional Inovasi Teknologi Pertanian: 1015-1026.
- [3] Badan Pusat Statistik.2014. Produksi Tomat. <http://www.bps.go.id>.
- [4] Linda Kusuma R, Firdaus M. 2015. Daya Saing dan Faktor yang Memengaruhi Volume Ekspor Sayuran Indonesia Terhadap Negara Tujuan Utama. *Jurnal Manajemen & Agribisnis* 12(3): 226-36.
- [5] Thirupathi, V., Sasikala, S., dan Z. Kennedy, J. Preservation of fruit and vegetables by wax coating,
In: Mittal, H. (Ed.), *Science and Entrepreneur*. NSTEDB. DST, Delhi, 2006, 1 -10.
- [6] Ifmalinda. 2017. Pengaruh Jenis Kemasan pada Penyimpanan Atmosfir Termodifikasi Buah Tomat. *Jurnal Teknologi Pertanian Andalas* 21(1): 1-7.
- [7] Parrotta, J A, 2001. *Healing Plants of Peninsular India*. CABI publishing.
- [8] Amalia Pranasari R, Indah Purwani K, Nurhidayati T. 2012. Persaingan Tanaman Jagung (*Zea mays*) dan Rumpuk Teki (*Cyperus rotundus*) Pada Pengaruh Cekaman Garam (NaCl). *Jurnal Sains dan Seni ITS* 1(1): 54-57.
- [9] Singh N, Pandey B R., Verma P, Bhalla M, Gilca M. 2012. Phyto-pharmacotherapeutics of *Cyperus Rotundus* Linn. (Motha): an Overview.
- [10] Rahmayanti R. 2016. Pemanfaatan Serbuk Rumpuk Teki (*Cyperus rotundus* L.) untuk Pengendalian Hama Gudang (*Tribolium castaneum*) pada Benih Jagung. Di dalam: Makalah Seminar Hasil. *Fakultas Pertanian Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta. Sains dan Seni ITS* 1(1): 54-57.
- [11] Bañez S E S, Castor L. 2011. Phytochemical and pesticidal properties of barsanga (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.). *JPAIR* 197.
- [12] Broto W, A Setyabudi D, Sunarmani, Qanytah, Badrul J I. 2017. Teknologi Penyimpanan Umbi Kentang (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) Var. Gm-05 Dengan Rekayasa Pencahayaan Untuk Mempertahankan Kesegarannya. *Jurnal Penelitian Pascapanen Pertanian* 14(2): 116-124.
- [13] Yongki A, Nurlina. 2014. Aplikasi Edible Coating dari Pektin Jeruk Songhi Pontianak (*Citrus nobilis* var. *Microcarpa*) pada Penyimpanan Buah Tomat. *JKK*.3(4): 11-20.
- [14] Pangalinan F R, Kojong N., dan Yamlean. 2012. *Uji Aktivitas Antijamur Ekstrak Etanol Kulit Batang Rambutan (Nephelium lappaceum L.) terhadap Jamur Candida Albicans Secara In Vitro*. Skripsi. Manado (ID): UNSTRAT.
- [15] Winarno F. G. dan M. A. Wirakartakusumah. 1981. *Fisiologi Lepas Panen*. PT. Sastra Hudaya.

Jakarta. 251 Hlm

- [16] Tano, K., R. K. Nery, M. Koussemon, dan M. K. Oule. 2008. The Effect of Different Storage Temperatures on The Quality of Fresh Bell Pepper (*Capsicum annum L.*). *Agricultural Journal* 3 (2) : 157-162
- [17] Nielsen, S.S. (2003). *Instructor Manual for Food Analysis; Answer to Study Question*. 3rd Edition. Kluwer Academic Plenum Publisher, New York. pp.154
- [18] Ravo, A., I. Baiamonte, dan F. Paoletti. 2002. Changes In Antioxidants and Taste - Related Compounds Content during Cold Storage of Fresh -Cut Red Sweet Peppers. *Eur Food Res Technol* 214 : 320–326
- [19] Millerd A J, Bonner B, B Jacob. 1952. *The Climacteric Rise In Fruit Respiration As Controlled by Phosphorylative Coupling*. *University of California*, Los angeles, California.

